

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Resources, Conservation & Recycling

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/resconrec

From resource extraction to manufacturing and construction: flows of stock-building materials in 177 countries from 1900 to 2016

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

material flow analysis
resource use
long-term analysis
uncertainty assessment
industrial ecology
social metabolism

ABSTRACT

Global material stocks of infrastructure, buildings, machinery and consumer products are growing rapidly, driving emissions and other environmental impacts during materials extraction, processing, construction and waste. However, international data on economy-wide material flows (ew-MFA) currently is limited to national extraction, trade and consumption and does not integrate material processing. Further developments for ew-MFA are required, ranging from more transparent data compilation and uncertainty assessments and improved representation of socio-economic material cycles to large spatio-temporal coverage. We herein present a novel ew-MFA database covering 14 major stock-building materials in 177 countries for the period 1900–2016. Included materials are, i.a., concrete, asphalt, bricks, timber, steel, aluminum, copper, other metals, plastics and glass. We developed a high-quality dataset by combining material flow accounting and analysis principles into a consistent 10-step compilation procedure, including the differentiation of processing stages from extraction to construction, as well as systematic uncertainty assessments. We find that global primary gross-additions-to-stock (GAS_{prim}) grew exponentially over almost the entire time period, largely in unison with GDP. In the year 2016, 39.7 ± 6.1 Gt/year of raw materials were extracted, of which 23% turned into waste during processing, resulting in 30.7 ± 5.7 Gt/year of GAS_{prim} . From the 1990s onwards, China outpaced all other countries in terms of annual per-capita GAS_{prim} and has dominated global dynamics since then. Across all countries, we find that per-capita GAS_{prim} and GDP decoupled over time. However, we find no indications for novel economic development pathways which are substantially less material-intensive in terms of stock-building than in the past.

Introduction

Socio-economic material stocks – that is, materials accumulated in infrastructures, buildings as well as capital and consumer products – are the material basis of socio-economic production and consumption. Global material stocks increased 23-fold in the 20th century and are expected to continue growing substantially in the coming decades (Elhacham et al., 2020; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017). Material stocks and the material and energy flows required for their construction, operation and replacement are of key importance for societal well-being and prosperity, as they are needed for the provision of services ('stock-flow-service nexus'; Haberl et al. (2017, 2021)). Crucial services requiring large material stocks include shelter, mobility, water, food, communication and many others (Brand-Correa & Steinberger, 2017; Pauliuk & Hertwich, 2015; Weisz et al., 2015). Providing services from materials, e.g., by utilizing roads and cars or by heating homes, requires

inputs of energy (Rao et al., 2019). In 2015, 75% of all extracted materials were used in manufacturing, construction, maintenance or operation of material stocks (Krausmann et al., 2018a).

Previous work showed, that a saturation of material stock levels is still out of reach across most world regions (Wiedenhofer et al., 2021): while industrialized regions show slow stock growth, China has become the main driver of global stock-flow dynamics since the 1990s. All other currently industrializing regions show stock growth rates of ~3–5%/year. No matter which modelling approach, all the literature expects substantial increases in global resource use over the next decades (Krausmann et al., 2018a, 2020; OECD, 2019; Plank et al., 2018; Schandl et al., 2016).

At the same time, resource extraction and processing of stock-building materials has become a major socio-ecological concern, as it drives increasing environmental pressures and impacts, making systematic and robust monitoring and improved data quality paramount

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.106122>

Received 14 September 2021; Received in revised form 15 December 2021; Accepted 17 December 2021

Available online 28 December 2021

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(Haberl et al., 2019; Sovacool et al., 2020; UNEP, 2019). Industrial extraction and processing of materials causes 25-35% of global GHG emissions (Hertwich, 2021; Lamb et al., 2021). Some of these materials-processing emissions are especially hard to decarbonize due to technological constraints (Allwood et al., 2010), for example, cement and steel production alone accounting for ~13% of global GHG emissions (Hertwich, 2021). Mining and processing of metals have been identified as major drivers of ecosystem and biodiversity impacts, emissions and negative social impacts (Luckeneder et al., 2021; Schaffartzik et al., 2016; Watari et al., 2021). Global sand extraction is growing globally and results in increasing pressures on local to regional socio-ecological systems (Torres et al., 2021). In addition to minerals and metals, the societal use of other stock-building materials like wood, plastics or glass also negatively affects our environment in various ways by contamination and exploitation of terrestrial and water ecosystems (Bais et al., 2015; Geyer et al., 2017; Westbroek et al., 2021). Against the backdrop of the need for a drastic reduction in GHG emissions to limit global warming to 1.5-2.0°Celsius over pre-industrial levels (IPCC, 2018), as well as efforts to drastically limit biodiversity loss (IPBES, 2019), more efficient uses and even reductions in materials demand seem required (UNEP, 2019).

Assessing resource use and informing strategies towards a more sustainable future therefore requires a robust and systematic knowledge base. However, our current knowledge on the dynamics of material cycles and socio-economic material stocks across time, countries and processing stages is limited and dispersed across studies and scopes (Graedel, 2019; Graedel et al., 2015; Krausmann, Schandl, et al., 2017; Watari et al., 2021). As a consequence, methodological developments to improve robustness, transparency, representation of socio-economic material cycles and spatio-temporal coverage are high on the agenda of the scientific community (Hertwich et al., 2018; Krausmann, Schandl, et al., 2017; Pauliuk, 2020; Pauliuk et al., 2016).

This research draws and combines the following strands of research: Firstly, economy-wide material flow accounts (ew-MFA) are widely used as policy indicators quantifying annual material flows in a manner that allows consistent comparisons across time and space at different scales, primarily for national economies (Eurostat, 2001; Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011; Moriguchi, 2007). However, the ew-MFA methodology is practically limited in quantifying socio-economic material cycles, as it treats the socio-economic system as a 'black box', with extraction of materials and energy inflows and outflows of waste and emissions (Krausmann, Schandl, et al., 2017; Wiedenhofer et al., 2019). Recently, efforts have begun to open up this 'black box' by integrating processes, stock dynamics and thereby fully mass-balancing to all outputs (Haas et al., 2020; Kovanda, 2021; Krausmann et al., 2018a; Schandl & Miatto, 2018; Schiller et al., 2017; Tanikawa et al., 2021). However, these efforts have not yet been extended comprehensively for all countries. Secondly, material or substance flow analyses (M/SFA) trace flows of specific materials or substances through socio-ecological systems, providing detailed information on processing stages, specific industries, technologies, even down to the fate of chemical elements (Brunner & Rechberger, 2020). Substantial efforts to gather high-quality data on material flows can be found throughout the literature (Graedel, et al., 2015; Lanau et al., 2019; Myers et al., 2019). However, variable system boundaries and different data compilation procedures hamper systematic integration of such data into more comprehensive databases, requiring further improvements on data quality, transparency and potentials for integration of results (ISIE-SEM section board, 2021).

With this paper and its linked MethodsX-paper, we contribute to addressing these research gaps in social metabolism research by presenting a centennial country-level ew-MFA database of 14 primary stock-building materials, distinguishing four processing steps from extraction to accumulation in stocks in a mass-balanced way. We trace material flows from extraction, to processing of raw and semi-finished products, to manufacturing and construction of final products, considering trade flows and processing wastes at each stage. We contribute to

improving data quality and transparency of ew-MFA by developing and presenting a consistent 10-step data compilation procedure and estimation methods, as well as a systematic uncertainty assessment, derived from a framework proposed by Laner et al. (2015). In a first empirical analysis of the data, we analyze the long-term trajectories, global patterns and uncertainties of primary gross additions to stocks (GAS_{prim}), i. e., the amount of primary materials used for stock-building in a country, on the global, regional and country level. We relate GAS_{prim} to population, GDP and gross fixed capital formation in order to detect different trajectories in resource use and efficiency, and to scrutinize the coupling of GAS_{prim} to economic development.

Analytic framework, methods and data sources

We here present an economy-wide quantification of primary material flows that are required to generate gross additions to stocks (GAS_{prim}) in 177 countries from 1900-2016. We develop this database through a combination of harmonized methods and principles from ew-MFA (Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017) and M/SFA (Brunner & Rechberger, 2020; Graedel, 2019), by developing a detailed, robustly and transparently compiled, fully mass-balanced ew-MFA dataset on material flows from extraction through processing of raw and semi-finished products to manufacturing and construction of final products. We distinguish processing stages using concepts that are commonly used in M/SFA and international databases (e.g. BGS, 2020; Graedel, 2019; Pauliuk, Wang, et al., 2013).

For the analysis, country-level data on population and gross domestic product (GDP) were compiled from several data sources (Fink-Jensen, 2015; MPD, 2018; UN, 2019, 2021). Data on gross fixed capital formation (GFCF, i.e. investments) was sourced from the UN national accounts database (UN, 2021) for the years 1970-2016. Details on the compilation procedures of these data and on the 177 countries included in our database (incl. region classifications) are provided in the linked MethodsX paper.

Consistently extending the ew-MFA framework with four processes

Figure 1 defines the system boundaries and gives an overview of the processes represented in the database, which are consistently extended from harmonized ew-MFA definitions (Fischer-Kowalski et al., 2011; Krausmann, Schandl, et al., 2017; Wiedenhofer et al., 2019). *Domestic extraction (DE, P1)* refers to the socio-economically used extraction of raw materials for the production of durable goods and infrastructures. Through mining, agriculture and logging, raw materials (e.g. limestone, ores or industrial roundwood) are extracted from the natural environment. These raw materials subsequently enter the stage of *refining and smelting of raw products (P2)*, where processing wastes occur (e.g. waste rock or bark) and raw products are produced (e.g. crude steel, cement or plastics). Raw products are then further processed during the *fabrication of semi-finished products (P3)*, resulting in semi-finished products (e.g. steel beams, concrete, paper) and processing wastes (e.g. sawdust, scrap). Semi-finished products are then during the *manufacture and construction of final products (P4)* turned into a broad variety of final products (e.g. buildings, infrastructure, machinery) which accumulate as in-use stocks; processing wastes (e.g. construction site losses, scrap) also occur in the manufacturing stage. A detailed description of processes, flows and system variables, following the MFA guidelines of the International Society of Industrial Ecology (ISIE-SEM section board, 2021), as well as further definitions and examples of materials and products at each processing stage are provided in the linked MethodsX paper.

Data sources and harmonization and compilation procedures

We use material-specific data sources, peer-reviewed and grey literature, as well as a 10-step compilation and estimation method, to

Figure 1. Definition of processes and material flows covered in the country-level database, including a visualization of the uncertainty assessment. Boxes indicate processes and arrows are material flows, which are consistently embedded into economy-wide material flow accounting principles (adapted from Wiedenhofer et al. (2019)). Processes and flows in yellow are quantified and presented in this database. The uncertainty assessment applied to each datapoint operationalizes the framework proposed by Laner et al. (2015), where five criteria are used to assess data quality and derive coefficients of variation (CV). Bal-item* indicates the sum of errors from yearly mass-balancing at each processing stage. A detailed definition on processes, flows and parameters as well as details on the uncertainty assessment can be found in the SI.

quantify yearly flows of 14 materials: concrete, asphalt, bricks, wood products, paper, iron & steel, aluminum, copper, zinc, lead, other metals, plastics, container glass and flat glass. The category ‘other metals’ contains only the respective fractions of chromium, manganese, tin and zinc that are not used in alloys with steel, aluminum or copper. Table 1 provides references to all major data sources that either constitute or validate the database, and also gives an overview on the spatio-temporal data coverage of the data sources.

For each material, exogenous data inputs for the compilation of the database comprise country-level production data, trade flows as well as several additional parameters. We collected production data mostly at the stage of raw products (P2), where comprehensive international data sources are available, with the exception of wood and paper, where FAOSTAT (2020) reports a high-quality dataset for semi-finished products (P3). Trade flows were sourced mostly from the Comtrade database (UN, 2020) for raw products (P2), semi-finished products (P3) and final products (P4), while the quantification of imports and exports of raw materials (P1) was outside the scope of this analysis, but could easily be integrated. For this paper, we therefore only quantify the extraction of raw materials related to stock-building on the global level, using raw-product-to-raw-material conversion factors compiled from various literature sources. For materials where production or trade data include secondary materials (i.e. recycled or down-cycled materials), we developed procedures to exclude these flows to ensure consistency of the

dataset with our goal of quantifying all primary stock-building materials. Processing wastes are explicitly quantified at each processing stage, distinguishing unrecoverable and recoverable processing wastes. According to the system boundaries, the recycling of recoverable processing waste of raw products is not quantified because it is considered as an internal flow within each process. Input of secondary materials (e.g. recovered end of life waste) are not considered, as the focus is here on primary material inputs to stocks. The quantification of end-of-life waste that enters waste treatment after the use phase, and a complete quantification of secondary material use is not included in this study and left for further research. A detailed documentation on the procedures developed to compile production and trade data for each material, on the exclusion of secondary materials and processing wastes as well as the mass-balancing to raw material extraction is provided in the linked MethodsX paper.

Data availability and quality across materials, years and sources varies greatly, as do exact definitions and coverage of the underlying data sources, especially for the historical time periods. We applied a consistent and clearly defined 10-step procedure to harmonize and compile data and applied a given sequence of correction and estimation methods to achieve a dataset covering all materials, years and countries. In these 10 steps, we: 1) identified, assessed, collected and digitized primary data sources; 2) conducted unit conversions and then sequenced and combined data sources to have one consistent dataset for each flow

Table 1

Sources for a country-level database for primary gross additions to stock. Main data sources were used primarily to compile the data, additional sources were used to complement and validate the data. Available time series and number of reported countries are referring to production data compiled from the main sources. Detailed information on data sources and compilation is provided in the linked MethodsX paper.

Material definition	Extracted raw materials in ew-MFA	Main data sources	Additional sources	Time series available	Nr. of reported countries
Concrete = Cement (+ sand and gravel)	Limestone, clay, sand and gravel	Production: CEMBUREAU (2017) ; Trade: CEMBUREAU (2017) , Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(Cao et al., 2017 ; CEMBUREAU, 2019 ; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017)	1913-2014	Almost all
Asphalt = Bitumen (+ sand and gravel)	Crude oil	Production: IEA (2018) , UNICPS (UNSD, 2019) ; Trade: IEA (2018)	(Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017 ; Miatto et al., 2017 ; Podobnik, 2006)	1950-2015	105
Bricks	Clays and kaolin	Production: UNICPS (UNSD, 2019) ; Trade: Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(Eil et al., 2020 ; Köstinger, 2021 ; Krausmann et al., 2018a ; Streeck et al., 2020, 2021 ; Wang et al., 2019)	1970-2016	65
Paper and paperboard	Industrial roundwood	Production: FAOSTAT (2020) ; Trade: Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(IPCC, 2019 ; van Ewijk et al., 2018, 2018)	1961-2016	Almost all
Solidwood products = sawnwood and wood-based panels	Industrial roundwood	Production: FAOSTAT (2020) ; Trade: Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(Bais et al., 2015 ; IPCC, 2019 ; Lawrence et al., 2010 ; Mantau, 2015 ; Ramage et al., 2017)	1961-2016	Almost all
Iron and steel = Casting iron and crude steel	Iron ore	Production: Pauliuk et al. (2013) until 1999, then (worldsteel 2020); Trade: Pauliuk et al (2013) , Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(BGS, 2020 ; Gauffin et al., 2016 ; Pauliuk, Milford, et al., 2013 ; USGS, 2020 ; Wang et al., 2007 ; WBMS, 2010, 2020b)	1900-2016	140
Aluminum	Bauxite	Production: BGS (1953) until 1950, then WBMS (2020a) ; Trade: BGS (1971) until 1962, then Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(BMLRT, 2020 ; IAI, 2017 ; Krausmann et al., 2018a ; Liu & Müller, 2013 ; USGS, 2020 ; Wang et al., 2018 ; WBMS, 2010, 2020b)	1913-2016	70
Copper	Copper ore	Production: BGS (1953) until 1950, then WBMS (2020a) ; Trade: BGS (1971) until 1962, then Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(BMLRT, 2020 ; Glöser et al., 2013 ; Krausmann et al., 2018a ; Soulmer et al., 2018 ; USGS, 2020 ; P. Wang et al., 2018 ; WBMS, 2010, 2020b)	1913-2016	70
Zinc	Zinc ore	Production: BGS (2020) ; Trade: BGS (2020)	(BMLRT, 2020 ; Krausmann et al., 2018a ; Meylan & Reck, 2017 ; USGS, 2020 ; Wang et al., 2018 ; WBMS, 2010, 2020b)	1913-2016	40
Lead	Lead ore	Production: BGS (2020) ; Trade: BGS (2020)	(BMLRT, 2020 ; Krausmann et al., 2018a ; USGS, 2020 ; Wang et al., 2018 ; WBMS, 2010, 2020b)	1913-2016	75
Other metals	Chromium, ore, manganese ore, nickel ore, tin ore	Production: BGS (2020) ; Trade: BGS (2020)	(BMLRT, 2020 ; Krausmann et al., 2018a ; USGS, 2020 ; Wang et al., 2018 ; WBMS, 2010, 2020b)	1913-2016	30-40
Plastics	Crude oil, natural gas	Production: IEA (2018) , UN energy (UNSD, 2020) , UNICPS (UNSD, 2019) ; Trade: Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(Babayemi et al., 2019 ; Euromap, 2016 ; Geyer et al., 2017 ; Jiang et al., 2020 ; Levi & Cullen, 2018 ; PlasticsEurope, 2019 ; PlasticsInsight, 2020 ; Ryberg et al., 2019)	1950-2016	120
Container glass	Limestone, silica sands, soda ash	Production: glassglobal (2020) , UNICPS (UNSD, 2019) , (Wiedenhofer et al., 2021); Trade: glassglobal (2020) , Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(Butler & Hooper, 2011, ; Glass Alliance Europe, 2019 ; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017 ; Marcu et al., 2014 ; Westbroek et al., 2021)(Butler and Hooper, 2019)	1970-2016	95
Flat glass	Limestone, silica sands, soda ash	Production: glassglobal (2020) , UNICPS (UNSD, 2019) , (Wiedenhofer et al., 2021); Trade: glassglobal (2020) , Comtrade (UN, 2020)	(Butler & Hooper, 2011, (Butler and Hooper, 2019) ; Glass Alliance Europe, 2019 ; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017 ; Marcu et al., 2014 ; Westbroek et al., 2021)	1970-2016	50

and material; 3) corrected for major changes in country definitions by considering major country fusions and dissolutions over the last century (e.g. the former Soviet Union, Czechoslovakia, Yugoslavia); 4) complemented and checked available time series by linear interpolation of data gaps, outlier corrections and cross-checks with the literature; 5) extrapolated non-available years for all countries into the past and the future using individual approaches for each material (e.g. by considering growth rates of related material flows, 'technological starting points', GDP and population trends); 6) applied material-specific estimation procedures to arrive at a sufficient country coverage for asphalt, wood, bricks, container and flat glass; 7) developed uncertainty estimates for each datapoint individually, which is further explained in the next paragraph; 8) derived production outputs by subtracting processing wastes; 9) established a mass-balance for each processing step by adding net-trade balances (imports minus exports) to production outputs; 10) calculated balancing items representing the globally accumulated error of data matching, stemming from ill-matched production and trade data. The 10-step procedure follows conservative, but systematic and transparent rules, which are explained in further detail in the related MethodsX paper.

Systematic uncertainty assessment and quantification

Due to the many estimations, decisions and expert judgements necessary to compile comprehensive and consistent ew-MFA datasets over long time periods, it has been increasingly recognized that a systematic assessment of data quality and quantification of uncertainty is required ([Džubur et al., 2016](#); [Patrício et al., 2015](#); [Wang & Ma, 2018](#); [Wiedenhofer et al., 2019](#)). We therefore conducted a systematic assessment of robustness and uncertainty for each datapoint in the database. We scored the reliability of the underlying data sources and all applied estimation procedures using the systematic evaluation framework proposed by [Laner et al. \(2015\)](#), which translates an ordinal scoring of data quality into normally distributed uncertainty ranges. The scoring is conducted for reported data along five independent data quality indicators (reliability, completeness, temporal correlation, geographical correlation and other correlation) and for expert judgements along a separate rationale ([Laner et al., 2015](#)) ([Fig. 1](#)). In our uncertainty assessment, we considered all data cleaning steps and estimation methods presented in the 10-step data compilation procedure, with the exception of unit conversions (e.g. volume to weight, \$ to kg) and the automatized data cleaning methods for primary trade data. In addition, we surveyed how many of the datapoints have been estimated

in comparison to the datapoints coming from data sources and how much these estimates account for of the total mass. Further information on the implementation of the uncertainty assessment and detailed results for each material can also be found in section 10 in the related MethodsX paper.

Results

In this results section, the 14 quantified materials are grouped into eight material groups for easier visualization: wood and paper are summarized, as are container glass and flat glass. “Non-ferrous metals” includes all metals except iron and steel, i.e. aluminum, copper, zinc, lead and other metals. Uncertainty ranges are always given as \pm - value and represent two normally-distributed standard deviations or 95% of the uncertainty distribution. The data shown in the figures can be found in the Supporting Information.

Tracing global primary materials from extraction, through processing to use

We traced the mass of all primary materials extracted per year through processing, manufacture and construction to inputs into final use as stock-building material. Figure 2 shows the global flows of these primary stock-building materials along the processing stages for the year 2016; figures for previous years can be found in section B1 in the Supporting Information (SI).

Global extraction of primary materials used for stock-building are estimated at 39.7 ± 6.1 Gt/yr for the year 2016 (Figure 2). Of the total extracted primary stock-building materials, 30.7 ± 5.7 Gt/yr, or 77%, enter the use phase. The residual 8.9 ± 1.7 Gt/yr are processing wastes ending up in waste management. Of these wastes, only a very small share of 5% are knowingly recoverable (most of which are metals), the rest is considered as unrecoverable processing losses. Quantitatively, most wastes occur during early production steps, i.e., processing raw materials into raw products (mostly stemming from waste rock and tailings), while later processing stages produce less waste.

In 2016 the materials entering the use phase are primarily concrete, making up the lion’s share of total GAS_{prim} (72%), bricks ranging second

(9%) and asphalt third (6%). In terms of extracted raw materials, these shares look rather different, with sand & gravel accounting for 57% of global extraction, limestone and clay both at 13%, iron ores and non-ferrous metal ores for 5% and 6%. This material composition changed dramatically over the last century. In 1950, concrete made up only 36% of total GAS_{prim} , asphalt 14%, bricks 25%, wood & paper 10% and iron & steel 7% (see section B1 in the SI). It is clear that concrete evolved to be the dominant construction material substituting all other options.

Global gross additions to stocks over time for primary materials

Material use for stock-building multiplied over the last 117 years. In 2016, global GAS_{prim} was about 30.7 ± 5.7 Gt/yr, which is a 43-fold increase since 1900 (0.7 ± 0.3 Gt/yr) (Figure 3a). While global GAS_{prim} grew moderately until 1950 (2.7 fold since 1900), the demand for stock-building materials increased strongly afterwards and accelerated again from 2000 onwards. GAS_{prim} doubled from 2000 to 2016, but decreased for the first time from 2014 to 2016. Our GAS_{prim} estimates correspond well with previous top-down global estimates (Krausmann et al., 2018b; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017; Wiedenhofer et al., 2019), which range at the top of our uncertainty range. We assume this difference to stem from the fact that our estimate is based on more detailed and national-scale data and distinguishes several processing steps and corresponding waste flows and losses. Further uncertainties and validations with other studies for each material are given in the related MethodsX article.

The 10-step data compilation procedures and the uncertainty assessment resulted in different uncertainty ranges over time and across the material groups (Figure 3b). In 2016, concrete represented the lion’s share of GAS_{prim} with 23.5 ± 3.8 Gt/yr and is responsible for the largest part of the total amount of uncertainty, while other materials like bricks (3 ± 1.1 Gt/yr), asphalt (2 ± 0.3 Gt/yr) or iron & steel (0.9 ± 0.1 Gt/yr) contribute less in absolute terms. However, in relative terms most uncertainty is found for bricks and glass ($\pm 38\%$), followed by plastics ($\pm 32\%$) and non-ferrous metals ($\pm 29\%$). Estimates for concrete, asphalt, wood & paper and iron & steel are considerably less uncertain, ranging between $\pm 15\text{--}17\%$, due to the much better availability of high-quality and relatively complete data sources for these materials (see section

Figure 2. Global primary stock-building materials traced from extraction via processing of raw, semi-finished and final products to use, 2016. Material definitions can change along the process chain (see table 2 in the related MethodsX paper).

Figure 3. Global primary gross additions to stocks (GAS_{prim}), including results on data quality and estimated uncertainty, which are given in ± 2 standard deviations (SD, 95% of total distribution). a) Global GAS_{prim} including total uncertainty and comparison to previous estimates on primary inputs to stocks (Krausmann et al., 2018b; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017); b) Global GAS_{prim} for different materials, including total uncertainty. Note that two scales are applied (concrete is given on the left axis, all other materials on the right). The shares of all datapoints and mass of GAS_{prim} that had to be estimated due to lacking data is shown in (c) and (d) as cumulative sum from 1900 to 2016, for c) materials (of raw products) and for d) total material flows of production and trade at the different processing stages.

2.2).

We also find that the share of datapoints that had to be estimated is generally larger than the thereby estimated mass flows. Figures 3c and 3d give an overview on the results from the 10-step data compilation procedure, especially for gap-filling that was necessary to derive the GAS_{prim} estimates, for each of the materials as well as for production and trade input datasets (more detail in the MethodsX article). Sand and gravel for concrete and bitumen are not shown here as they are 100% estimated using technical coefficients. For most materials, the estimated share of datapoints is higher than the estimated mass, because most data that needed to be estimated was for early historical years, when consumption levels were low. The only exceptions are glass, for which most datapoints had to be estimated, and bitumen, for which the disaggregation of the former Soviet Union into its successor states resulted in a higher estimated share of total mass, although being based on reported data.

For the process stages, we find that the estimated share of total mass is only higher than the estimated datapoints for the refining & smelting stage (30 vs 19%) (P2, in Figure 1). This can mostly be traced back to wood and bricks, as industrial roundwood and bricks account for a rather large share of total production (when not showing sand & gravel), for which we had to estimate comparatively large flows. In contrast, for physical trade most datapoints that had to be estimated only account for a small share of the total mass of traded materials.

Development and composition of primary gross additions to stock across income groups and countries

Here we provide an analysis of the relations of primary material use for stock-building across 116 years of resource use for all 177 countries grouped into four income groups, based on the World Bank classifications for the year 2016 (World Bank, 2019). Distinctions are made based on the gross national product per capita (in US\$) in 2016: low-income countries range below 1005 US\$/cap, lower-middle-income countries from 1006 - 3955 US\$/cap, upper-middle-income countries from 3956 - 12235 US\$/cap and high-income countries above that. The low-income group includes 31 countries in our database, the lower-middle-income group 48 countries, the upper-middle-income group 46 countries and the high-income group 52 countries (see the related MethodsX article for the list of countries and groups).

We find that the shares of each income group in global GAS_{prim} changed significantly over the last century (Figure 4). In 1950, high-income countries used 60% of global GAS_{prim} , while upper-middle income countries only accounted for 27%, lower-middle income countries 12% and lower-income countries only 1%. Already in 1985, upper-middle-income countries (mostly dominated by China) overtook high-income countries in absolute terms, showing contrasting trajectories. In 2000, upper-middle-income countries already accounted for half of global GAS_{prim} , while high-income countries' share constantly decreased and lower-middle-income and low-income countries' share slightly increased. Dynamics picked up speed after 2000 and upper-

Figure 4. Total GAS_{prim} for four World Bank (2019) income groups, distinguished by materials, and summed up to the global account, 1900-2016.

Figure 5. GAS_{prim} per capita of all 177 countries grouped into four income groups of the World Bank (2019), from 1900-2016. Mean of region represents the total GAS_{prim} of the income group divided by its population, mean/median of countries the average mean/median of per-capita GAS_{prim} of all countries in the respective income group. The grey area represents the 5%- & 95%-percentile of GAS_{prim} per capita of countries in the respective income group. Note that mean of region and mean of countries strongly deviate in the upper-middle-income group as China dominates due to its large population and material use.

middle-income, lower-middle-income and low-income countries accelerated their demand for GAS_{prim} drastically. In 2016, high-income countries only accounted for 15% of global GAS_{prim} (4.6 ±0.9 Gt/yr), upper-middle-income countries already for 66% (20.2 ±3.6 Gt/yr), lower-middle-income for 18% (5.3 ±1.1 Gt/yr) and low-income for 2% (0.5 ±0.2 Gt/yr).

The material composition of GAS_{prim} also differs across the income groups and over time (Figure 4). During the last century, concrete partly replaced bricks and wood in all regions, however bricks remained of high importance in lower-income countries. We also find that asphalt, mostly used for road construction and maintenance, is primarily used in the high-income countries. In 2016, GAS_{prim} of high-income countries consisted to 59% of concrete, a comparatively large share of asphalt (20%), only 3% of bricks and 17% of all other stock-building materials. GAS_{prim} of upper-middle-income countries were clearly dominated by concrete (82%), 4% of asphalt, 8% of bricks and 5% of all other materials. GAS_{prim} of lower-middle-income countries consisted to 73% of concrete, 4% of asphalt, 19% of bricks and 4% of other materials and GAS_{prim} of low-income countries to 70% of concrete, only 1% of asphalt, 25% of bricks and 5% of other materials.

Income groups and countries show diverse levels and trajectories of GAS_{prim} also in per-capita terms (Figure 5). We find that high-income countries' per-capita GAS_{prim} remained rather steady in the first half

of the 20th century and then accelerated between ~1945 to the 1970s, where it then stabilized at a relatively high level and large spread across all countries in this group. Interestingly, from 2008 onwards, average GAS_{prim} per-capita decreased considerably in the years following the global financial crisis, to about 4 tons/cap/year. This applies to the mean of regions and the median of countries, while the mean of countries follows a similar trend at a slightly higher level. Furthermore, the range of per-capita values in high-income countries are consistently higher than for all other regions.

From 2000 onwards, China outpaced all other countries, even in per-capita terms, and has determined the global dynamic since then (Figure 5). For the group of upper-middle-income countries, China is dominating the mean of the whole region due to its large population as well as its rapid GAS_{prim} per capita growth. Mean and median of countries of the upper-middle-income group are far below the regional mean, as most other countries in this group did not yet reach per-capita GAS_{prim} levels of high-income countries. Per-capita GAS_{prim} of lower-middle-income countries started to increase more strongly after 2000, although still only reaching ~2 tons/cap/year in 2016. The low-income countries group however remains at a very low level of only ~1 tons/cap/year of GAS_{prim} per capita, with the higher range of per-capita values in this group barely reaching 2 tons/cap/year.

Figure 6. Correlations between per-capita GAS_{prim} and per-capita GDP (left) or GFCF (right) for all countries, for 1970 (upper figures) and 2016 (lower figures). Colours indicate affiliation to one of the World Bank (2019) income groups. Note that x- & y-scales are decadic logarithmic, numbers therefore have to be read as 10^x. The regression line represents a standard linear regression model, the respective equation and R²-value are given for each graph.

Resource efficiency, construction and stock-building: correlations of GAS_{prim} with GDP and GFCF

By relating per-capita GAS_{prim} to per-capita GDP, we can analyze the correlation of primary material demand for stock-building with economic development. Additionally, we related GAS_{prim} per capita to gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), to explore the resource intensity of investments into fixed capital (material stocks). By calculating linear regressions and the goodness-of-fit R^2 , we can also make statements on the direction and strength of the correlation. All variables are given on decadic logarithmic scales, so regression coefficients should be interpreted as elasticities, i.e. a 1% change in per-capita GDP or GFCF is associated with an x% change in per-capita GAS_{prim} .

We find that the coupling between per-capita GAS_{prim} and both GDP and GFCF decreased strongly, as indicated by flatter regression lines in 2016 compared to 1970 (Figure 6). In 1970, a 1% increase in per-capita GDP was associated with a 1.21% increase in GAS_{prim} , i.e. GAS_{prim} was hyper-coupled to GDP. In 2016, a 1% increase in per-capita GDP was associated with only a 0.48% increase in GAS_{prim} , i.e. GAS_{prim} increases half as much as GDP across all countries, which indicates relative decoupling. This indicates that per-capita GAS_{prim} converged over time, while GDP diverged. For GFCF we find similar patterns, although with generally lower correlation coefficients (Figure 6). In 1970, a 1% increase in per-capita GFCF was associated with a 0.69% increase in GAS_{prim} , i.e. GAS_{prim} was relatively decoupled from GFCF. In 2016, a 1% per-capita GFCF increase was correlated with a 0.36% increase in GAS_{prim} . Correlations between per-capita GAS_{prim} and both GDP and GFCF are both relatively strong, but languished over time (R^2 : 0.83 in 1970 and 0.73 or 0.71 in 2016).

These findings indicate that economies tend to become more efficient in using primary bulk materials for stock-building to generate economic growth and in their investments into fixed capital, i.e. primary material use relatively decoupled from economic development. However, this trend is more pronounced for GDP than for GFCF, as the regression coefficients decreased stronger for GDP (-60%) than for GFCF (-48%). GFCF, i.e. investments into fixed capital, which is then used in future production and value creation, therefore seem to decouple slower than GDP. However, it has to be noted that these correlations only cover bulk materials, while economic development increasingly also requires rare earths, technology-critical elements or complex compounds and amalgamates, e.g. for micro-electronics (Graedel, et al., 2015).

Relating long-term developments of these three indicators globally and for the income groups (shown in section B2 in the SI) reveals that global GAS_{prim} was strongly coupled to GDP growth from 1970 to 2014. Only for the years 2015 and 2016 a relative decoupling of global GAS_{prim} from GDP occurred. Trends across income groups differ strongly: While GAS_{prim} remained rather stable and strongly decoupled from GDP growth in high-income countries, GAS_{prim} was hyper-coupled to GDP in upper-middle-income countries and lower-income countries and is tightly coupled to GDP in lower-middle-income countries. Our findings therefore also show that global development dynamics differ strongly: while industrialized countries tend to rely less on material stock build-up for their economies, partially because they already have high stock levels (Wiedenhofer et al., 2021), it seems that further infrastructure development and urbanization in the currently industrializing countries, often seen as a precondition for economic growth, will continue to drive material use for stock-building.

When investigating correlations for materials separately (results are shown in section B3 in the SI), correlations of GAS_{prim} and GDP in year 2016 are strongest for glass (R^2 : 0.87, $\alpha=1.2$), asphalt (R^2 : 0.84, $\alpha=1.46$), wood, paper and metals (R^2 : 0.79, $\alpha=0.85$) and plastics (R^2 : 0.76, $\alpha=0.85$), less pronounced for concrete (R^2 : 0.53, $\alpha=0.46$) and very weak for bricks (R^2 : 0.1, $\alpha=0.12$). Glass, asphalt, wood and paper, metals and plastics therefore seem to be closely connected with economic development, whereas especially for bricks but also for concrete the relationship is more ambiguous in 2016. The case of bricks is

particularly interesting as both magnitude and strength of the relationship decrease strongest among all materials, from $R^2=0.52$ and $\alpha=0.88$ in 1970, to R^2 : 0.1 and $\alpha=0.12$ in 2016, which indicates that while in earlier decades GAS_{prim} for bricks and GDP were relatively coupled, in recent years there is no explanatory power of GDP levels for annual bricks use.

Discussion

We presented and analyzed a novel ew-MFA database of all primary bulk materials used for constructing materials stocks for 177 countries from 1900-2016. This research also provides methodological novelty, integrating material flow *accounting* and *analysis* principles along ew-MFA system boundaries, distinguishing four processes and their related trade flows, as well as a consistent and transparent 10-step compilation procedure, including a full uncertainty assessment.

Improving data quality and uncertainty assessments in ew-MFA

Uncertainty analysis and data reconciliation based on systematic statistical frameworks, as well as the reporting of uncertainties in publications, is underdeveloped in ew-MFA studies (Krausmann, Schandl, et al., 2017; Laner et al., 2014). Our database was compiled applying systematic and transparent data compilation procedures as well as a fully operationalized uncertainty assessment framework based on Laner et al. (2015). We systematically quantified and presented the impacts of the 10-step data compilation procedures in terms of number of estimated datapoints and estimated total mass in detail for each material (Figure 2 and section 10.5 in the linked MethodsX paper).

Most material flows prior to 1960 are estimated, due to a lack of historical data in international data sources. Where available, long-term ew-MFA country case studies were used to complement international data (Table 1). Overall, while many datapoints were estimated for early decades, the share of estimated mass flows of total flows for each material remain low, since resource use in the early decades of the 20th century was generally lower. Our GAS_{prim} estimates and their uncertainty ranges are in good agreement with other studies quantifying global or regional GAS_{prim} (Krausmann et al., 2018b; Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017; Wiedenhofer et al., 2019). However, the previous estimates tend to be higher for some materials than the estimates presented here, which we explain with the additional efforts undertaken to compile this dataset, i.e., by accounting on the country-level and properly excluding double-counting, secondary material flows and processing wastes. Details on the uncertainty assessment, validations and further uncertainty ranges for individual materials are reported in section 10 in the linked MethodsX paper.

Based on Figure 2 and the materials-specific assessment in the MethodsX paper, we argue that the quality and robustness of the overall dataset is good, given that this is an economy-wide global country-level database and not a material- or country-specific effort. Only for glass, bricks and partially wood products, and for early decades we gauge the quality and robustness of the overall dataset to be only intermediate. Further in-depth studies will be necessary to improve data quality for these materials, whose results can then be integrated into updates of this database.

To systematize the assessment of data quality differences and uncertainties between materials, countries and years, we assigned ordinal data quality and uncertainty scores to each datapoint. Using the framework of Laner et al. (2015), we translated these ordinal scores into continuous coefficients of variation (CV), via a translation function that needs to be chosen by the practitioner depending on context, aims and scope. In this implementation, we decided to limit total maximum uncertainty to $\pm 100\%$, which constrains uncertainty to a minimum of zero, so as to not violate the mass-balance principle. The resulting uncertainty ranges are primarily a relative uncertainty assessment reflecting data availability and required data compilation procedures between

materials, countries and over time, and secondly a quantification of absolute uncertainties based the authors' expert judgements following extensive work with these data sources. Uncertainties are generally larger for early decades, especially prior to 1960 as many datapoints had to be estimated for these years, and lower for countries that report complete data time series (e.g. UK, USA).

While scoring the general reliability of international databases, we could not consider differences in the reliability of primary data collection and reporting across countries from the same source, due to a lack of reported information. Uncertainties of GAS_{prim} of lower income countries might therefore be underestimated in relation to higher income countries with well-developed reporting systems. Varying quality of reported statistical data from the same source/reporting institution across countries should be considered in future work and will require collaboration with those institutions and stakeholders. Additionally, exploring other translation functions from scoring to CVs, as well as other non-normally distributed uncertainty ranges could help to improve representation of potential under- or overestimations. Further work on specific materials, countries and years can easily be integrated into this database and contribute to improved data quality scoring and thereby reduce uncertainties. We conclude that this operationalization of an uncertainty assessment does work in an ew-MFA context and constitutes a fruitful further avenue for improving data quality and robustness.

Global primary material inputs to stocks, socio-economic development and climate change mitigation

Humanity has built up a huge stock of materials in buildings, infrastructures and machinery. Recent studies have revealed that human-made mass amounts to approximately 1000 Gt and is now roughly equal to all living biomass on the planet and continues to grow at high rates (Elhacham et al., 2020; Krausmann et al., 2020). Building-up and maintaining this stock requires large and continuous inputs of materials. Comparing the results on the yearly input of primary stock building materials from our national scale database with total material extraction as reported in the UNEP-IRP database (UN-IRP, 2018), we find that the share of raw materials used for stock building in total global material extraction has increased from 33% in 1970 to 44% in 2016. This share would even be higher when considering sand & gravel for road base-courses and buildings (Krausmann, Wiedenhofer, et al., 2017), which we excluded from our analysis.

While we find a slowdown of growth in GAS_{prim} and more recently even a considerable reduction in high income countries since the 2008 financial crisis, absolute and per capita levels in all other income groups have accelerated drastically since around the year 2000. We find that there seems to be an ongoing catch-up and potential future convergence of per-capita GAS_{prim} across countries and income groups. The reasons for the sudden, but so far lasting decline of GAS_{prim} in the HI group are unclear. A bundle of factors might be relevant, including a slow-down of stock expansion in the high-income countries, potentially upcoming future saturations of stocks in some countries, low infrastructure investments and also an increasing use of secondary materials (Haas et al., 2020; Streeck et al., 2020, 2021; Wiedenhofer et al., 2021).

A first-ever reduction of global GAS_{prim} occurred at the very end of the observed time period, when GAS_{prim} fell by 1.7% between 2014 and 2016. Whether this indicates a turning point for global material use must be doubted, considering that regional trends indicate either stabilization or growth. The decline in global GAS_{prim} after 2014 seems to be mainly caused by a reduction of growth in China related to a slowdown of economic growth, a shift in economic policy and a (potentially only temporary) peak in construction activities (Gosens & Jotzo, 2020; Huang et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020). Overall, we find that China plays a dominating role for global stock building and is one of the few emerging economies which actually has caught up with the high-income countries. Rapid urbanization and build-up of infrastructures in China

has driven its per-capita GAS_{prim} even to more than twice the average of the high-income group. In the lower-income groups, per-capita flows are at a very low level but are growing (78% lower than in the high-income countries). Building-up material stocks to provide essential services for a growing population in large parts of the world is likely to continue to be an important driver for rising global demand in GAS_{prim} in the coming decades.

The need to improve living conditions in many countries, for example to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (Thacker et al., 2019), clearly justifies further stock build-up. However, the question arises if living conditions could be improved in a less material- and emissions-intensive manner (Grubler et al., 2018; O'Neill et al., 2018; Rao & Wilson, 2021). Capitalistic mass production and consumption building upon the excessive use of natural resources does not necessarily have to be the best and only option to fulfill human needs and contribute to human well-being (Wiedmann et al., 2020). Recent research suggests that social progress depends not only on resource and energy flows and efficiencies, or the creation of value added (GDP), but rather on the services derived from material stocks of buildings, infrastructure and machinery (Graedel et al., 2015; Haberl et al., 2017, 2019; Mayer et al., 2017). A sufficient and socially acceptable level of material stocks and services provided through constant or even shrinking resource use within ecological limits therefore constitutes a crucial research frontier (Fuchs et al., 2021; O'Neill, 2015; O'Neill et al., 2018).

Importantly, the further pursuit of past material-intensive development has large implications for environmental pressures and especially GHG emissions. Materials extraction, processing and production causes 25-35% of global GHG emissions (Hertwich, 2021; Lamb et al., 2021). In the near future, large volumes of material use and related emissions might be expected, e.g. for a growing building stock in China and Africa (Huang et al., 2013; Tenaw & Hawitibo, 2021). For example, Krausmann et al. (2020) estimated that a continuation of material-intensive stock buildup across the world to achieve similar high levels of material stocks, including resulting energy requirements for stock operation, could consume a substantial share of the 1.5-2°C target's carbon budget. This indicates that material efficiency, the circular economy and demand-side solutions for more efficient but less stocks could become crucial contributions to mitigating the climate crisis (Haas et al., 2020; Lamb et al., 2021; Pauliuk et al., 2021; Zhong et al., 2021).

Conclusions

With this novel database and the methods for advancing spatio-temporal coverage, robustness and uncertainty assessment, we contribute to improving data quality and transparency in the social metabolism and industrial ecology community. Our database provides insights into different trajectories of the use of stock-building materials and is the basis for inflow-driven dynamic MFA modelling and the corresponding flows of wastes and secondary materials at the resolution of national economies (Wiedenhofer et al., 2019). It furthermore can be used for assessments of material efficiency strategies (Hertwich et al., 2019; Pauliuk & Heeren, 2021), explorations of the materials-energy-GHG nexus (Cantzer et al., 2020; Hertwich, 2019), as well as assessing stock-flow-service nexus relations (Haberl et al., 2017, 2019). By consistently linking extraction to the use of materials on a country-level, it also delivers data essential to assess environmental impacts of these material flows along each process from extraction, refining & smelting, to manufacturing and construction. It can therefore contribute to further developing and informing monitoring of (un)sustainable resource use patterns and help inform global research and policy (UNEP-IRP, 2019).

We find that the middle-income countries, especially China, are catching up with per-capita material use of high-income countries. Per-capita values accelerate slowly in low-income countries, indicating substantial requirements for future resource use. To provide essential services from material stocks for the growing population in large parts of

the world will drive global demand of stock-building materials in the coming decades. We do find that economic development is becoming relatively decoupled from primary material use for stock-building. However, so far, we found no indications for the emergence of novel development pathways that seem to be substantially less material-intensive than in past times. Finding new ways to provide a sufficient and socially acceptable level of material stocks and derived essential services for all people on this planet therefore seems crucial for achieving more sustainable resource use patterns.

Author contribution statement

Barbara Plank: conceptualization, methodology, validation, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, visualization, writing – original draft & revision

Jan Streeck: methodology, visualization, investigation, writing – original draft & revision

Doris Virág: investigation, visualization, writing – original draft

Fridolin Krausmann: conceptualization, methodology, supervision, writing – original draft & revision

Helmut Haberl: conceptualization, supervision, funding acquisition, writing – original draft & revision

Dominik Wiedenhofer: conceptualization, methodology, visualization, supervision, writing – original draft & revision, project administration

Supporting information

In supplementary information (SI) A, we provide the data used for the figures presented in this article. In SI B, we present additional results from our economy-wide database on primary material flows from extraction through four processing stages, systematically covering and estimating 177 countries from 1900–2016. We present global primary flows for earlier decades, resource efficiencies for income groups over time and country-level resource efficiencies per material.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovative programme (MAT STOCKS, grant agreement No 741950) and Austrian Science Fund (FWF) (Project MISO P27590). We thank Quirin Damermer, Vivianne Rau and André Baumgart for their contribution to data compilation and two anonymous reviewers for their helpful comments.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.106122](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.106122).

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